

PROBLEMS OF ENSURING LEGALITY IN OPERATIONAL-SEARCH ACTIVITY

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Ensuring legality in operational-search activity is directly related to the fundamental guarantees of human rights and freedoms in a legal state.

In its essence, operational-search activity consists of the process of obtaining information related to a person.¹ Ensuring legality in operational-search activity is directly related to the fundamental guarantees of human rights and freedoms in a legal state.

In its essence, operational-search activity is directly related to the restriction of the inviolability of private life and other constitutional rights.

Therefore, along with other mechanisms for ensuring legality in OSA, the creation of an impartial and stable control system, as a component of these mechanisms, is required.

In addition, the legislation regulating OSA must be improved based on new forms and threats of crime — that is, it must not lag behind law enforcement practice. Otherwise, relations not regulated by law will be filled with unlawful practices.

Thus, the problems of ensuring legality in OSA consist of the following:

1. Problems in the legal regulation of OSA.

Although many operational-search measures resemble investigative actions from the point of view of restricting individual rights, they are not fully regulated legally or are regulated by departmental documents.

Since most departmental documents are not publicly disclosed, it is impossible to evaluate the legality of OSMs conducted on the basis of such documents.

Moreover, some legal acts regulating OSA are not harmonized with the Law on OSA, and OSMs conducted by various agencies are not unified.

For example, in the Regulation on the organization of the use of technical means of the operational-search activity system in telecommunication networks of the Republic of Uzbekistan, approved by Presidential Decision No. PQ-513 of November 21, 2006, such concepts as the operational-search activity system in

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telecommunication networks (SORM), its technical means, and the powers of the authorized body are defined.

In particular, Clauses 40–41 of the Regulation impose an obligation on telecommunication operators to provide the authorized body with personal information on an unlimited range of individuals.

At the same time, this Regulation was adopted before the Law on OSA was enacted and was not brought into compliance with the law.

Operational-search measures regulating the fight against new forms of crime, cybercrime, and transnational crime are not regulated legally.

2. Weakness of the control system over OSA.

The lack of judicial oversight over OSA and the closed, formal nature of prosecutorial supervision, the absence of a system for assessing the legality of OSMs sanctioned by the prosecutor, and the fact that the departmental evaluation system is based not on the protection of individual rights but on achieved results negatively affect the effectiveness of control.

3. Problems related to the protection of human rights.

The primary goal is considered to be achieving the objectives of OSA rather than ensuring the inviolability of private life and constitutional rights of the individual.

Persons who are the subject of OSA have limited means of protecting their rights, including being informed of OSMs conducted against them and filing a complaint in court for violations of their rights.

Abuse of OSA capabilities by the implementing bodies, cases of provocation of crime to improve performance indicators, and falsification of evidence and OSA results are present.

4. Lack of parliamentary and public oversight over OSA.

There is no practice of parliamentary or public evaluation of the legality of OSA, despite the fact that general information about OSA, its effectiveness, and the degree of restriction of individual rights during OSA — although not state secrets — are closed.

5. Restriction of the individual's freedom of movement in OSA.

During OSA, individuals suspected of committing a crime or witnesses are brought to law enforcement bodies and held in order to obtain written explanations.

However, under current legislation, detention is permitted only in accordance with the CPC or the Administrative Code.

According to Article 285 of the Administrative Code, administrative detention is carried out to stop an administrative offense and identify the offender's identity and thus is not applicable to operational-search activity.

The fact that persons brought in during OSA do not have the procedural status of witness or suspect leads to violations of their rights.

In the laws regulating the activities of some authorized bodies conducting OSA (for example, Article 17 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Internal Affairs Bodies"), the right to detain persons suspected of committing a crime is specified — but this only refers to detention in a procedural manner.

6. Other forms of restriction of rights in OSA are related to restriction of the right to defense.

Although Article 29 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan guarantees the right of everyone to receive qualified legal assistance, this norm applies not only to persons with procedural status but to any person, including those subject to overt OSMs.

Article 48 of the CPC partially regulates this issue — it provides that after the operational-search measure has actually ended, the person has the right to use the assistance of a defense lawyer.

However, in the Law on OSA, the participation of a defense lawyer in overt OSMs is not provided for.

Given that the results of many operational-search measures form the basis for initiating a criminal case and prosecuting a person, the importance of the right to legal assistance for a person subject to OSMs becomes clear.

7. Violations of the inviolability of residence during OSA.

Violations of the law related to the breach of the inviolability of residence frequently occur in the OSA process.

The problem lies in the doctrinal mismatch between the traditional concept of inviolability of residence and the capabilities of modern technical means.

Today, technical tools allow for visual surveillance of a residence and recording of sounds inside it without physical entry — that is, without physically violating the inviolability of the residence.

The conditions for conducting operational-search measures (OSMs) should be understood as a set of principles and rules enshrined in the law that ensure a balance between, on the one hand, the interests of a person who has the right to the inviolability of private life, and on the other hand, the interests of society interested in the effective fight against crime.²

It is necessary to especially note that the conditions for conducting operational-search measures (OSMs) as defined in the Law are not perfect and are insufficient for protecting a person's constitutional rights.

In particular, the Law does not specify:

- the degree of severity of crimes for which interception of conversations via telephones and other telecommunications devices and acquisition of information transmitted through them, or conducting of operational experiments, may be allowed;
- the time limits for conducting OSMs that restrict constitutional rights of individuals;
- against whom exactly the interception of conversations via phones and other telecommunications devices and the acquisition of information through them may be applied;
- that the mere fact of an operational file being compiled on a person should not serve as a basis for restricting their rights;
- that the right to property may only be restricted in relation to instruments and objects of crime, or items prohibited from circulation — all of which negatively affects the level of protection of individual rights in OSA.

The process of digitalization, which encompasses all areas of life, has certainly not bypassed criminal procedural relations.

The shift of criminal activity into the digital world requires the identification of digital traces of crime.

In this context, the seizure and subsequent inspection of electronic devices containing electronic data and digital evidence during OSA requires clarification regarding how much it restricts a person's rights to correspondence, phone conversations, and other communications.

In this context, a person's rights may be restricted during OSA by inspecting the memory of an electronic carrier (phone, computer) that was seized, and by reviewing the person's accounts on internet platforms.

According to Article 135 of the Criminal Procedure Code, items, documents, and electronic data found during seizure and search must be inspected in accordance with the rules established for conducting these investigative actions.

However, in the Law "On Operational-Search Activity," seizure is not provided for — instead, within the framework of the OSM "inspection of residences and other places, buildings, structures, land plots, technical and transport means," the inspection of computers and communication devices is allowed.

That is, the inspection of communication devices belonging to a person is carried out without seizure according to the CPC, and whether coercive elements are present or not in such OSMs is not regulated.

The second problem is accessing a person's account on social networks and retrieving data from it without seizing their communication device.

That is, in the seizure report, it is recorded as if the data from the person's account was obtained with their consent, but in reality, the voluntariness of that consent (given while the person was brought to the law enforcement building with restricted freedom of movement) is questionable.

In practice, the password to the account is obtained and personal conversations on social networks are reviewed.

Therefore, a question arises about what kind of operational-search action this is and its legal nature — but in any case, such an action restricts a person's constitutional rights.

Some scholars have proposed applying a new model for authorizing OSMs that restrict constitutional rights — namely, collecting personal information about an individual on the basis of a court decision by recording the individual's connection to the crime, and thereby authorizing all such operational-search measures at once by restricting constitutional rights.³

While the author's position—that any form of collection of personal data should be subject to prior judicial authorization—is both reasonable and consistent with constitutional guarantees, the proposal to simultaneously authorize all operational-search measures based solely on a preliminary indication of a person's involvement in a crime is problematic.

Such an approach not only contradicts the presumption of innocence and the principle of proportionality enshrined in the Constitution, but also fails to recognize the distinct legal nature, objectives, and scope of each operational-search measure.

By disregarding these differences, this model risks indiscriminately restricting multiple fundamental rights at once, without the individualized assessment necessary to ensure lawful and proportionate interference.

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